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EFFECTS OF THE DRUG THIOGAMMA® ON THE SYMPTOMS OF PERIPHERAL DIABETIC POLYNEUROPATHY, AS WELL AS EVALUATION OF THE MENTAL STATUS IN PATIENTS WITH DIABETES MELLITUS AND OTHER DISORDERS OF CARBOHYDRATE METABOLISM

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ABSTRACT

Loss of sensation in the feet and symptoms of muscle weakness are the main signs of peripheral diabetic polyneuropathy. The main problem of endocrinologists and other specialists in the field of diabetology is the difficulty of early diagnosis of the above complication of diabetes. In addition, the treatment of diabetic polyneuropathy is complicated by poor compensation, which may be associated with cognitive impairment in DM patients due to specific brain disorders. In our study, we assessed Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE) mental status and Neuropathy Impairment Score — Low Limbs (NIS-LL) symptoms of muscle weakness and tenderness with Thiogamma® (Worwag Pharma) in 635 patients with diabetes and other disorders of carbohydrate metabolism.

Keywords: diabetes mellitus, diabetic polyneuropathy, MMSE scale, NIS-LL scale, alpha-lipoic (thioctic) acid.

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ВЛИЯНИЯ ПРЕПАРАТА ТИОГАММА® НА СИМПТОМЫ ПЕРИФЕРИЧЕСКОЙ ДИАБЕТИЧЕСКОЙ ПОЛИНЕЙРОПАТИИ, А ТАКЖЕ ОЦЕНКА ПСИХИЧЕСКОГО СТАТУСА У ПАЦИЕНТОВ САХАРНЫМ ДИАБЕТОМ И ДРУГИМИ НАРУШЕНИЯМИ УГЛЕВОДНОГО ОБМЕНА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Нарушения чувствительности стоп и симптомы мышечной слабости являются главными признаками периферической диабетической полинейропатии. Главной проблемой эндокринологов и других специалистов в области диабетологии является трудность ранней диагностики вышеуказанного осложнения СД. К тому же, лечение диабетической полинейропатии осложняется плохой компенсацией, которая может быть ассоциирована нарушениями когнитивных функций у пациентов СД в следствии специфических нарушений головного мозга. В нашем исследовании мы провели оценку психического статуса по шкале Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE) и симптомов мышечной слабости и чувствительности по шкале Neuropathy Impairment Score — Low Limbs (NIS-LL) при применении препарата Тиогамма® (компании Worwag Pharma) у 635 пациентов с СД и другими нарушениями углеводного обмена.

Ключевые слова: сахарный диабет, диабетическая полинейропатия, шкала MMSE, шкала NIS-LL, альфа- липоевая (тиоктовая) кислота.

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ТИОГАММА® DORI VOSITASINING PERIFERIK DABETIK POLINEYROPATIYA BELGILARIGA TA'SIRI, SHUNINGDEK QANDLI DIABET VA BOSHQA UGLEVOD ALMASHINUVI BUZILISHLARI BOR BEMORLARNING RUHIY HOLATINI BAHOLASH

ANNOTASIYA

Oyoqlarda sezuvchanlikni yo'qotish va mushaklar kuchsizligi belgilari periferik diabetik polinevopatiyaning asosiy belgilaridir. Endokrinologlar va diabetologiya sohasidagi boshqa mutaxassislarining asosiy muammosi diabetning yuqoridagi asoratini erta tashxislash qiyinligidadir. Bundan tashqari, diabetik polineyropatiyani davolash yomon kompensatsiya bilan murakkablashadi, bu esa o'ziga xos bosh miyaning ma'lum buzilishlari tufayli QD bemorlarida kognitiv buzilish bilan bog'liq bo'lishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: qandli diabet, diabetik polineyropatiya, MMSE shkalasi, NIS-LL shkalasi, alfa-lipoik (tioktik) kislota.

Introduction.

One of the most common and difficult to treat complications DM is diabetic neuropathy (DN). According to different authors, the prevalence of DN in the population of DM patients ranges from 10% to 63% [3, 4]. The probability of detecting DN using various diagnostic tests varies from 28.6% with a traditional neurological examination to 75.5 and 100%, respectively, with a vibration sensitivity study and during electroneuromyography. The incidence of this complication increases with the age of patients, as well as with increasing duration of diabetes. After 10-20 years, DN is detected in about half of patients. However, the incidence of polyneuropathy depends not only on the duration of the underlying disease, but also on the effectiveness of hypoglycemic therapy [11]. But

there is not always a direct relationship between the severity and the likelihood of developing polyneuropathy,

Peripheral polyneuropathy is subdivided into somatic primary lesion of sensory or motor nerve fibers and autonomic. The clinical picture consists of components of positive symptoms: motor (nighttime muscle cramps) and sensory (tingling, tension, goosebumps, pain, burning, numbness); negative symptoms: motor (weakness, atrophy) and sensory (decrease in tactile, pain, temperature types of sensitivity and articular feeling). Symptoms of autonomic neuropathy are dizziness when changing body position, palpitations at rest, dry skin, a feeling of a full stomach, nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, impotence, dysuria. Active clinical symptoms of diabetic polyneuropathy with the development of a pronounced pain syndrome often led to a significant deterioration in the quality of life of patients; to progressive amyotrophy,

The main focus in the prevention and treatment of diabetic neuropathy is the correction of carbohydrate metabolism. But strict control of the level of glycemia and glycated hemoglobin ($HbA1c < 7.0\%$) is not achievable in most patients, which causes additional use of drugs. In this regard, it is relevant to search and study the effectiveness of the use of drugs that can prevent the development and progression of neurological complications from both medical and social points of view.

There is a lot of information about the effectiveness of alpha-lipoic (thioctic) acid in treatment of diabetic polyneuropathy (ALADIN, ALADIN III, ORPIL, SYDNEY, DEKAN, etc.) [1, 5, 9, 13, 15]. This substance forms the chemical basis of the drug under the trade name Thiogamma® (Worwag Pharma). Thiogamma® acts as a coenzyme of a complex of enzymes involved in the oxidative decarboxylation of alpha-keto acids; enhances glucose transport and has a positive effect on cell energy metabolism by activating mitochondrial enzymes; inhibits the processes of gluconeogenesis and ketogenesis, which contributes to the normalization of metabolic processes and compensation of the disease, inhibits the processes of excessive non-enzymatic glycation. According to the results of the SYDNEY 2 study, the optimal dose for oral administration is 600 mg once a day [12]. The DEKAN (Deutsche Kardiale Autonome Neuropathie) study showed that

A number of studies have shown that the presence and duration of DM are associated with cognitive impairment and dementia [7], which, in turn, negatively affect the course of DM and its complications, making it difficult for patients to learn adherence to therapy and self-control methods. This is evidenced by studies that have shown the relationship between high levels of glycemia and glycated hemoglobin and cognitive impairment [2,10] both in patients with type 2 diabetes and in patients with type 1 diabetes. According to a number of researchers, the causes of these disorders in patients with DM can be vascular factors (vascular atherosclerosis, circulatory disorders, arterial hypertension), neurodegenerative changes (Alzheimer's disease), episodes of hypoglycemia, and insulin resistance. The Honolulu-Asia Aging Study has confirmed the link between diabetes, vascular and neurodegenerative changes in the brain, confirmed by MRI. 38% of patients in the study cohort had DM; the presence of diabetes increased the risk of lacunar changes (adjusted risk 1.6, confidence interval 1.0–2.6) and hippocampal atrophy (adjusted risk 1.7 [CI 0.9–2.9]). These changes may be anatomical prerequisites for an increased risk of cognitive impairment and dementia [6]. The high incidence of type 2 diabetes mellitus in the elderly, coupled with the age-related risk of cognitive impairment, leads to the fact that cognitive impairment has become a serious problem in diabetology.

In connection with the above, the purpose of the study was to study the effect of the drug Thiogamma® for symptoms of muscle weakness and sensitive symptoms, as well as assessment of mental status in patients with impaired carbohydrate metabolism.

Main part.

In the study, 635 patients with impaired carbohydrate metabolism and DM (27 patients (4%) with type 1 DM, 602 people (96%) with type 2 DM, 6 (1%) with other types of carbohydrate metabolism disorders), selected in accordance with the following criteria: DM 1 or 2 types of both sexes (from 18 to 70 years old); the presence of severe distal symmetric sensorimotor polyneuropathy. The patients were in the stage of subcompensation of the underlying disease, the initial level of $HbA1c < 9\%$. All patients received appropriate individualized antihyperglycemic therapy. Of these,

372 people were women (58.5%), 263 (41.5%) were men. 89 patients (14%) were under 45 years of age, 546 patients (86%) were over 45 years of age. The exclusion criteria were: allergy to the components of the drug, pregnancy, period; peripheral arterial disease; renal, hepatic insufficiency; oncological diseases; concomitant severe somatic and mental illness; severe diseases of the cardiovascular system, cardiac arrhythmias; other diseases of the endocrine system; neurological diseases; vitamin therapy during the last 4 weeks; previous therapy with other drugs used to treat diabetic polyneuropathy within the last 4 weeks; alcohol abuse.

All patients gave written informed consent to participate in clinical trials.

In accordance with the protocol, all patients were examined before the start of the study and after 3 and 6 weeks on the background of drug treatment. The clinical characteristics of the patients are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Clinical characteristics of patients included in the study.

Index	Group (in / in) + tab. 600 mg.
Number of patients	635
Gender (male/female).	263/372
Age, years	56.1±4.8
DM 1 type (n)/DM 2 type (n)/other types (n)	27/602/6
HbA1c (%)	8.4±0.6
Accompanying illnesses	
1. Arterial hypertension (hypertension) (n)	
2. Ischemic heart disease (n)	102 (16%)
3. Hypothyroidism (n)	18 (2.8%)
4. Chronic cholecystitis (n)	8 (1.2%)
5. Obesity (n)	21 (3.3%)
6. Vegetovascular dystonia (n)	20 (3.3%)
7. Chronic pancreatitis (n)	9 (1.2%)
8. Chronic pyelonephritis (n)	14 (2.2%)
9. History of stroke in anamnesis (n)	11 (1.7%)
10. Diabetic polyneuropathy (radiculopathy) (n)	6 (0.9%)
	106 (16.7%)
NSS-Score (points)	7.4±0.8
Duration of treatment	6 months

Clinical study of the severity of peripheral sensorimotor neuropathy consisted of 1) mental status assessment (Mini-Mental State Examination, MMSE); 2) evaluation of symptoms of muscle weakness and sensitivity (Neuropathy Impairment Score - Low Limbs - NIS-LL). These survey methods are based on the subjective feelings of patients. The Mini Mental Status Assessment (MMSE) assessed the cognitive abilities of patients in terms of the following indicators: orientation in time and place, perception, concentration and calculation, memory and speech. The maximum score was 30 points. Neuropathic symptoms and their changes were assessed using the Neuropathy Impairment Score — Low Limbs (NIS-LL) questionnaire. This questionnaire method evaluates changes in the symptoms of muscle weakness and sensitivity on 9 indicators of subjective sensation.

Research results

Drug tolerance.

The present study initially included 635 diabetic patients and other disorders of carbohydrate metabolism. One patient withdrew from the study as a result of the development of an allergic reaction after the 5th intravenous infusion of 600 mg Thiogamma, in 1 patient an allergy developed after 6 monthss course of treatment, all studies of this patient are included in the results.

Dynamics of neurological symptoms.

Decreased activity and intensity of neurological symptoms (pain, burning, numbness, paresthesia of the lower extremities) was noted already at 7-8 infusions. Only in 1 patient with type 1 diabetes out of 27, after the first 3 injections, discomfort (hyperesthesia), pain in the legs, especially at night, intensified. The increase in neurological symptoms is explained not so much by the influence of Thiogamma, but by the beginning of intensive insulin therapy. Improvement in NIS-LL scores was observed in 97.07% of patients, 2.8% of patients showed no changes, and 1.13% of patients showed negative dynamics of scores.

Considering separately the various indicators of the NIS-LL scale, there were observed different changes in the indicators of symptoms of muscle weakness (Fig. 1) and sensitivity (Fig. 2).

Figure 1. Changes in symptom scores of muscle weakness.

Figure 2. Changes in sensitivity symptom scores.

Mental status was assessed using the Mini-Mental State Examination scale, MMSE. Evaluation of the results showed that 45 patients (7%) had no impairment, 84 patients (13.2%) had mild cognitive impairment, 182 patients (28.7%) had moderate cognitive impairment, 285 patients (44.9%) had mild

dementia, 39 patients (6.1%) had moderate dementia (Figure 3). Severe dementia was not recorded in any of the patients.

Figure 3. Mental status assessment results.

Thus, our study confirmed the high therapeutic the effectiveness of Thiogamma® at a dose of 600 and 1200 mg in peripheral sensory neuropathies. The best effect was observed at a dose of 600 mg, when using Thiogamma® first by infusion, then orally for 6 months. In addition, this study confirmed the excellent tolerability of Thiogamma® at a dose of 600 and 1200 mg. But, according to the literature, side effects increased at a dose of 1200 mg. Based on the consideration that the most important is the ratio of benefit of treatment and risk, our study determined the dose of 600 mg as optimal, which is consistent with other studies.

Analyzing the obtained data, we came to the conclusion that Thiogamma® (Worwag Pharma) is the drug of first choice in the treatment of various forms of diabetic polyneuropathy. Correct adequate administration of effective doses and compliance with the duration of treatment against the background of diabetes compensation will allow not only to obtain a significant clinical effect in the manifest stage of diabetic neuropathy, but also to prevent the occurrence of these complications in the early preclinical stages.

Conclusions.

1. Treatment of distal diabetic polyneuropathy with Thiogamma® leads to a significant reduction in the symptoms of neuropathy Neuropathy Impairment Score - Low Limbs (NIS-LL).
2. The decrease in symptoms of distal diabetic polyneuropathy is accompanied by an improvement in the neurological status: a decrease in the symptoms of muscle weakness (weakness in the legs such that when walking the foot slaps, weakness in which it is impossible to walk on tiptoe tactilely, weakness in the muscles of the pelvic girdle and hips, in which it is difficult to climb or descend stairs, getting up from a chair or sofa (having to help with hands) and improving sensory symptoms (pain sensitivity).
3. The safety of using high doses of Thiogamma® 600 mg and 1200 mg in patients with diabetes has been confirmed.

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